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French Polynesia - observation of cultural influences from the United States. A sightseeing and tourist expedition in 2005

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ABSTRACT

This report presents the beauty culture of French Polynesia and cultural influences from the United States. The expedition took place at the turn of June and July in 2005. The visited islands are Tahiti and Moorea. It was found that the islands of Tahiti and Moorea, while being close, can be distinguished by significant cultural differences and standard of living.

Keywords: French Polynesia, Tahiti, Moorea, cultural influences, American lifestyle invasion

INTRODUCTION

Tahiti, Bora Bora, etc., – the mythical, even divine islands of French Polynesia have been famous for many hundred years for their beauty of nature, landscapes and friendly people. Thanks to this information, for many years I have wanted to see the beauty of these islands. At the turn of June and July 2005, I decided to go there. I flew from Poland via Frankfurt (Germany), San Paulo (Brazil), Santiago (Chile) to Tahiti (French Polynesia) (Photo 1).

Already at the airport ‘Tahiti Faaa’ I was greeted by Polynesian music and I received one very fragrant flower as a gift: “Tiare Tahiti (Tiare Maohi)”, *Gardenia tahitensis* DC, (Photo 2 & 3).

After leaving the airport, the climate turned out to be hot and humid. Hotels were expensive so I slept on the beach. The omnipresent mosquitoes made life difficult at every step, especially at night when you were sleeping.

On the main island of French Polynesia – Tahiti, during some ceremony I noticed influences from the United States: American cars, motorcycles, USA flags, etc.

So Tahiti has become Americanised, noise and exhaust fumes are the priority of this ceremony (Photos: 4 to 11). Coca Cola, burgers, and things like that – these are the main factors of obesity in Tahitians.

In Photo 12, you can see the rain coming on the island of Tahiti. It got me wet, but it was pleasant because it was warm.

The next day I took the ferry from Tahiti to the island of Moorea. This Moorea Island is located west of the island of Tahiti. The climate is similar here: warm and humid. Mosquitoes and biting beach midges make it difficult to sleep on the beach at night. I walked the entire island of Moorea with a backpack It took me two days (Photos 13 to 25). The island of Moorea is a very lovely island, quiet and peaceful, with beautiful beaches, suitable for retirees to live in. Photos 26 and 27, photos of postcards as souvenirs from Tahiti. Photo 28 shows a CD I bought in Tahiti with Polynesian songs. After listening to it in Poland, it turned out that the music is mostly electronic ...

CONCLUSIONS

The invasion of the American lifestyle and way of being on the island of Tahiti is ubiquitous. Moorea Island, although not far west of Tahiti, has a different way of life: peace, quiet, albeit more modest but free life.

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Appendix

Photo 1.

Photo 2.

Photo 3.

Photo 4.

Photo 5.

Photo 6.

Photo 7.

Photo 8.

Photo 9.

Photo 10.

Photo 11.

Photo 12.

Photo 13.

Photo 14.

Photo 15.

Photo 16.

Photo 17.

Photo 18.

Photo 19.

Photo 20.

Photo 21.

Photo 22.

Photo 23.

Photo 24.

Photo 25.

Bons baisers de Tikehau

Photo 26.

Photo 27.

Photo 28.